

Notes

Conductometric and Spectrophotometric Studies on Scandium(III), Yttrium(III) and Lanthanum(III) Complexes with Violuric Acid

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VIOLURIC acid (5-oximinobarbituric acid) is of great use as a good organic chelating agent and a metal indicator for the analytical determination of minute amounts of transition metals. It was introduced as an indicator¹ for the complexometric titration of copper with complexon II. It is also used for the gravimetric microdetermination of palladium², for the photometric determination of copper³, and for the spectrophotometric studies⁴ of its V^V, Nb^V and Ta^V complexes. Sc^{III} and La^{III} chelates with alizarin red S and quinizarin sulphonic acid were studied spectrophotometrically and conductometrically⁵. Scandium was also studied spectrophotometrically using xylenol orange as a complexing agent^{6,7}.

Experimental

Solutions (10⁻³M) of Sc^{III}, Y^{III} or La^{III} were prepared^{8,9} by dissolving appropriate quantities of the A.R. grade (99.9%) Sc(NO₃)₃·4H₂O, Y₂(SO₄)₃ and La(NO₃)₃·6H₂O in double distilled water. Violuric acid solution (10⁻²M) was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of reagent in double distilled water. Oxalic, boric, succinic acids, Na₂SO₄, Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O and Na₂CO₃ buffers of pH 1.83-11.31 were prepared¹⁰ and standardised using pH meter.

Uv spectra was recorded on Pye Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer, using 1 cm silica cell. Pye Unicam model 290 MK 2 pH meter and Solu. Bridge, REG. U.S. PAT. OFF. Soil Tester, RD B15 Ser. 34621 were used.

Procedure: The conductometric titrations were carried out by titrating a known volume (V₁) of the metal ions with 0.5 ml increments of violuric acid (VA) (V₂), then measuring the specific conductivity after 2 min stirring and correcting the conductance due to dilution effect. Conductometric measurements were made using constant concentration of the metal ions and variable concentration of VA keeping the total volume constant, then thermostating the solutions at 30° for 2 h. The spectrophotometric measurements were performed at 200-300 nm. The reference solution was prepared by mixing the metal ion with the ligand-buffer

mixture using a blank solution containing the same [VA] in the same buffer as in the test solution of the metal ion.

Results and Discussion

Conductance values obtained during the titration of Sc^{III}, Y^{III} and La^{III} increase with the increase of [VA]. Increase of conductance may be as a result of the liberation of H⁺ ions from violuric acid which increase the conducting power of the solution leading to complex formation^{11,12}.

The spectrograms of Sc^{III}-, Y^{III}- and La^{III}-violurates are characterised by one peak. The spectral absorbance of the complexes is influenced by the following factors.

(i) **Effect of pH:** The spectral absorbance of the solutions of the complexes were measured at 200-300 nm using a series of buffer solutions (pH 1.83-11.31). The absorbance of the solutions of complexes increased with increasing pH reaching the maximum development of complex formation at pH 9.83 for Sc^{III} (λ_{max} =228 nm), 7.7 for Y^{III} (λ_{max} =240 nm) and 8.83 for La^{III} complex (λ_{max} =235 nm), and then slowed down. Observation of different bands may be due to the progressive formation of different convertible species of complexes. Shift to longer wavelength may be attributed to the formation of complexes absorbing lesser amounts of energy than those appearing at shorter wavelengths (absorbing large amounts of energy). Shift to shorter wavelength may be due to a shift in ionisation which denotes that the π - π^* transitions within the heterocyclic ring are influenced by inter- and intra-molecular charge transfer.

(ii) **Effect of ligand concentration:** The concentrations of Sc^{III} and La^{III} (5 × 10⁻⁶M) and Y^{III} (10⁻⁴M) was kept constant, and [VA] changed in the range 10⁻⁵-2.5 × 10⁻⁴M in the case of Sc^{III} and La^{III} and 2 × 10⁻⁵-6 × 10⁻⁴M in the case of Y^{III} complexes. The spectral absorbance increased gradually with the increase of [VA] due to gradual complex formation having large ligand concentration, then approached a limiting value. As [VA] increases, λ_{max} shifts to longer wavelengths as a result of an intramolecular charge transfer and a π - π^* transition through the heterocyclic system.

(iii) **Effect of metal ion concentration:** The [VA] was held constant at 1 × 10⁻⁴M in the case of Sc^{III} and La^{III}, and 2 × 10⁻⁴M in the case of Y^{III}, whereas the concentration of Sc^{III} and La^{III} was changed from 5 × 10⁻⁶ to 1.8 × 10⁻⁴M and that of Y^{III} from 1 × 10⁻⁵ to 4 × 10⁻⁴M. The absorbance of the solutions increased apparently.

Beer's law is valid for the microanalytical determination of 2.25 ppm Sc ($\epsilon=8 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 8.89 ppm Y ($\epsilon=1.9 \times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 11.11 ppm La ($\epsilon=7.5 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

NOTES

TABLE 1—EVALUATION OF STOICHIOMETRY, CONDITIONAL STABILITY CONSTANT (K_f) AND FREE ENERGY ($\Delta^\circ G$ IN kcal mol⁻¹ AT 25°) OF Sc^{III}-, Y^{III}- AND La^{III}- VIOLURATE COMPLEXES

Method	Ratio	Sc ^{III} -violurate		Y ^{III} -violurate		La ^{III} -violurate	
		K_f	$\Delta^\circ G$	K_f	$\Delta^\circ G$	K_f	$\Delta^\circ G$
M.R.	1:1						
	1:2	0.21 × 10 ¹³	16.927	0.095 × 10 ⁷	8.203	13.636 × 10 ¹¹	16.653
	1:3	4.97 × 10 ¹⁰	25.658	0.53 × 10 ¹⁷	22.952	1.56 × 10 ¹⁵	20.85
	1:4	0.292 × 10 ²⁰	26.713	11.53 × 10 ²⁰	28.904	0.252 × 10 ¹⁷	22.404
C.V.	2:1	0.148 × 10 ⁶	7.095				
	1:1	0.803 × 10 ⁹	10.276	0.03 × 10 ⁹	8.888	0.45 × 10 ⁹	10.503
	1:2	1.254 × 10 ¹³	16.602	0.155 × 10 ¹³	15.357	9.932 × 10 ¹³	17.836
	1:4	0.345 × 10 ²⁰	268.19	3.56 × 10 ²⁰	28.204	2.141 × 10 ²³	30.645
S.L.	1:1	2.63 × 10 ¹⁰	14.30	19.395 × 10 ¹³	18.225	0.12 × 10 ⁹	9.715
	1:2	1.022 × 10 ¹⁶	21.97			10.74 × 10 ¹⁷	24.745
L.L.	1:1	0.049 × 10 ⁷	7.809	0.02 × 10 ⁴	3.158	0.018 × 10 ⁴	3.095
pH	1:1	0.267 × 10 ⁹	10.192	0.138 × 10 ⁶	7.054	0.135 × 10 ⁷	8.413

Stoichiometry of the complexes: The composition of Sc^{III}, Y^{III} and La^{III} complexes was determined from conductometric titrations, conductometric measurements and spectrophotometric methods (molar ratio, M.R.¹⁵; continuous variation, C.V.^{14,15}; straight line, S.L.¹⁶; and limiting logararithmic, L.L.¹⁸ methods). The results obtained are recorded in Table 1.

The conditional formation constant: The conditional stability constants of the complexes were evaluated making use of the results of the spectrophotometric methods¹³⁻¹⁶ and the analytical (A-pH) method¹⁰. The free energy change ($\Delta^\circ G$) of the complexes was calculated using the relation

$$\Delta^\circ G = -RT \ln k.$$

The results of stoichiometry, stability constant and free energy of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The data indicate that the stability of the complexes are in the order La^{III}->Y^{III}->Sc^{III}-violurates.

The complexation takes place through covalent linkage between the central metal ion and the C-OH group, and coordination between the central metal ion and the nitroso group²⁰. Complexation through covalent linkage is confirmed from the results of the conductivity experiments. The results show an increase in conductance values with the increase of [VA] as a result of increasing conducting power of the solutions containing ionic species (H⁺ ions) liberated due to dissociation of the ligand which manifests the gradual increase of the molar conductivity of the solution. The mobility of the hydrogen ions liberated, moves faster and gather enhanced electrical field and thus increases the conductivity of the solution. Linkage between violuric acid and the metal ions in the complexes (1:1) can be typified as follows:

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Spectral Studies on Bis-(β -Naphthylidene-*o*-amino phenolato) Chelates of Cerium(III), Samarium(III), Gadolinium(III), Dysprosium(III), Cobalt(II) and Chromium(III)

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Ce^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III}, Co^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes of tridentate Schiff base derived from the condensation of *o*-aminophenol and β -naphthylglyoxal have been prepared and studied by